

Implementation of a Measurement-based Care Depression Protocol

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Background

- Quantifying the progress and outcomes of patients in the behavioral health (BH) setting is challenging
- Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) in the US is a common BH diagnosis, estimated at 7% prevalence
- Measurement-based care (MBC) to monitor BH outcomes is evidence-based practice, but not often adopted
- The Joint Commission (TJC) requires MBC in BH settings to quantify clinical change

Purpose

- This was a quality improvement project to support TJC Behavioral Health Care Outcomes Measure Standard
- The goal was to develop, implement, and evaluate a new MDD protocol based on the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9)

Methods

Participants:

- Nurses/nurse practitioners
- Social workers
- Therapists

Instruments:

- Inservice education (4 domains)
- PHQ-9 (de-identified scores)
- New MBC Depression Protocol
- New data collection tool (with embedded calculations and graphing)

Three metric sets:

- Impact of in-service education
- Protocol adherence by staff
- Aggregate Patient response (PHQ-9 score change)

Tool Development

Measurement-Based Care of Depression Protocol at the St. Joseph Hospital of Orange (abbreviated)

Discussion

- In-service education resulted in ~1/3 improvement from pre to post-education. The most challenging questions related to the new protocol
- Protocol adherence was high in the outpatient setting due to familiarity with PHQ-9
- Aggregate PHQ-9 score reduction may indicate an improved response rate to treatment (e.g., >50% from initial score)

Limitations

- Short duration of study resulted in incomplete inpatient implementation
- Small sample size for de-identified PHQ-9 scores

Recommendations

- Extend MBC protocol implementation to inpatient setting and to other BH diagnoses

Conclusions

- A protocol was successfully set up and adhered to in the outpatient BH setting
- The data collection tool with embedded calculations and graphing function facilitated data analysis and reporting to support JC measure
- PHQ-9 monitoring may function as a "lab" test for depression
- MBC will lead to improved patient-centric care by quantifying outcomes of care, treatment, and services

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Results

1. BH Staff In-service Education and Confidence Scores (n=38, n=44)

2. Protocol Adherence by Outpatient Staff: Met target of 3 (100%) PHQ-9 surveys per patient

3. Aggregate Patient Response

Outpatient improvement in PHQ-9 scores (n=20) from admission to discharge of 56% (facility average episode of care 4-6 weeks)

% of MDD Patients by PHQ-9 Score Change

